

BENEFITS OF NUTRITIONAL MONITORING IN THE TREATMENT OF CHILDHOOD OBESITY ACCORDING TO THE LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

When analyzing the world scenario on obesity, it is evident that this is an urgent health issue that needs to be much discussed. Brazil is part of the group of countries that are at the top of the obesity list, one of the options to start changing this scenario is prevention and focusing a lot on treatment, especially for children, since an obese child has very high chances of taking this obesity into adulthood. This study has the general objective of identifying the benefits that nutritional monitoring brings to obese children according to the literature. To achieve this objective, the methodology used was a systematic literature review. According to what was designed, it worked with a qualitative and structure, that is, it did not use a statistical reference as the basis of the analysis process of a problem. After carrying out the literature review, it was found that nutritional monitoring helps to reduce weight and BMI, therefore it is a great tool in the treatment of childhood obesity. It concludes that nutritional monitoring is essential in the prevention and treatment of childhood obesity.

Keywords: Nutrition. Obesity. Bad Nutrition.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that by 2025, more than 70 million people will be obese and about 2.3 billion will be overweight. And studies on these numbers argue that heredity alone does not justify this large proportion. Studies indicate that this increase is linked to the environment, that is: increased intake of sugar and saturated fats, low fiber consumption, emotional aspects and, since the 1980s, reduced physical exercise.

Obesity should not be seen only as an aesthetic problem, which bothers because of criticism and bullying. Excess weight can lead to the emergence of various health problems such as diabetes, heart problems and poor skeletal formation in children.

Children usually gain weight more easily because of factors such as: wrong eating habits, genetic inclination, sedentary lifestyle, psychological disorders, problems in family life,

among others. Many people think that obese children are obese because they eat too much. But this thought is not always true, because obese children usually consume high-calorie food that does not need to be in large quantities to cause weight gain.

There is a network of prepared and qualified professionals to treat obesity in adults and children. And one of them is the nutritionist who can help a lot through nutritional monitoring, which is a complete check of the patient's nutritional condition, forming an individualized food program, with the intention of achieving the goals in a healthy way.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a systematic bibliographic review that was carried out in August 2022. According to what was designed, it worked with a qualitative and descriptive structure, that is, it did not use a statistical reference as the basis of the process of analyzing a problem. This study was carried out through a bibliographical research with a search for scientific articles, theses and monographs on the subject: the benefits of nutritional monitoring in the treatment of childhood obesity according to the literature, in the following databases: Lilacs and Virtual Library in Health (VHL) found by the descriptors: Eating behavior; Child obesity; Food and nutrition. To carry out the crossing, all the descriptors mentioned above were used.

51 articles were found in Lilacs and 579 in VHL, totaling 629 articles. The process for separating the material found was based on directed reading and filing; the inclusion criteria were the publication period between 2012 and 2021, being free, in English, Portuguese and Spanish, available in full, being related to the theme. The exclusion criteria of the articles were for not having a connection with the theme, publication before 2012, being paid, being available in other languages and being incomplete. After this separation, 10 articles were selected for the composition of this study.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Nutritional monitoring aimed at controlling childhood obesity has been much sought after in recent years. This monitoring is essential for the care of children who have irregular nutritional status, as it seeks to develop healthy habits in the child, and the correct consumption of food, focusing on essential nutrients for their stage of life, reducing the risks and complications of obesity. . (HONICKY; KÜHL; MELHEM 2017)

Childhood obesity has treatment and the choice of treatment needs to be based on the severity of the problem and the presence of associated complications. The main goal of weight loss is to reduce or adjust the amount of body fat to reduce the risk of future complications. (VENEZIAN, 2021)

Nutritional monitoring based on the adoption of a healthy diet, aimed at adjusting the amount of calories, food preferences, financial aspects and lifestyle, together with physical activity, are important aspects for the treatment of childhood obesity. (ANTUNES, 2018)

Franchini, Schmidt and Deon (2018), carried out a study with 102 who presented weight, pre-obesity and obesity, all children underwent three nutritional interventions with the nutritionist and presented a reduction of 1.87% in weight, concluding then that nutritional interventions through food education activities are efficient in reducing the weight of obese children.

In the research by Honicky, Kühn and Melhem (2017), nutritional intervention in children with obesity for six months, a considerable reduction in BMI was observed, a factor that greatly favors the improvement of obesity in children and increases the quality of life of this population .

The performance of the nutritionist through group therapy is very important to treat obese infants, promoting an improvement in their quality of life (TABORDA; MAZUR; SCHMITT, 2020). The authors Testa, Poeta and Duarte (2017), concluded in their study that children with obesity, when submitted to nutritional monitoring, obtain a reduction in BMI as a result.

Poet et al. (2013), carried out a study with 32 obese children, the children were divided into 2 groups (group with intervention and group without intervention), at the end of the intervention program with physical activities and nutritional guidance, the children in the group that received the interventions showed a significant reduction in BMI from 26.4 kg/m² to 25.5 kg/m², in addition to improvements in the physical, emotional, social, psychosocial domains and in general quality of life.

Oliveira et al. (2019), when evaluating nutritional interventions for obese and malnourished children, found that a food distribution program for children with malnutrition, and the practice of physical exercises and nutritional guidance for children with obesity, are important. So they concluded that nutritional interventions are relevant to prevent or treat food shortages or excesses.

When evaluating the impact of an intervention project for childhood obesity on the eating behaviors and physical activity of 381 children who attended between the 1st and 4th grade of elementary school, after 3 years of implementation, Rodrigues, Alves and Amorim

(2015) , found overweight children became normoweight, since the average values of physical activity were low, but adequate eating behaviors.

When starting a healthy diet, consuming daily portions recommended by the WHO and Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) literature, that is, following the recommended dietary intake of carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, vitamins and minerals. These nutrients are found in fruits, vegetables, rice, oilseeds, which consumed correctly and regularly helps reduce weight and can help fight obesity. (ANTUNES, 2018)

A nutritional follow-up also helps to reduce the consumption of foods with sugar and saturated fats, mainly present in industrially processed fats (hydrogenated), red meat, butter, and full-fat dairy products, and this also helps in reducing weight and can reflect positively on the treatment. of obesity. (CAVALCANTI, 2019)

Nutritional monitoring helps in the control and treatment of childhood obesity, but it also helps in the prevention and treatment of diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, hypertension and other pathologies that can be directly linked to poor diet. (TABORDA; MAZUR; SCHMITT, 2020)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Childhood obesity is a very serious problem for public health and it needs to be prevented and treated as soon as possible. The fight is not easy and involves a multidisciplinary team, and the nutritionist fits perfectly into this team, being able to help both the child and the parents.

Nutritional monitoring is essential for the care of children who have irregular nutritional status, as it seeks to develop healthy habits in the child, and the correct consumption of food, focusing on essential nutrients for their stage of life, reducing the risks and complications of obesity . That is, it assists in maintaining the correct and regular diet that helps in reducing weight and can help fight obesity.

After carrying out the bibliographical research, it was evident that nutritional monitoring, when carried out with obese children, helps to reduce weight and BMI. This happens due to dietary changes because monitoring helps to reduce the consumption of foods with sugar and saturated fats, present mainly in industrially processed fats, red meat, butter, and full-fat dairy products and this also helps in weight reduction and can reflect positively in the treatment of obesity.

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